

**ISSUES OF USING TRADITIONAL AND MODERN
METHODS IN LANGUAGE TEACHING**

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the use of traditional and modern methods in language teaching and their impact on educational effectiveness. The study shows the importance of traditional methods in creating a theoretical foundation and the role of modern methods in forming communicative competence.

In the current era of globalization, increasing the effectiveness of foreign language teaching is one of the priority tasks of the educational process. From this point of view, the harmonious use of traditional and modern methods significantly increases the quality of the learning process. First of all, traditional methods were formed as a classical direction of language teaching, which serve to consistently master theoretical knowledge. The most popular among traditional methods are the grammar-translation method, the direct method, and the audiolingual method. These three traditional methods were mainly aimed at providing knowledge about the language and were based on the following principles:

1. A thorough analysis of the target language, especially its grammar;
2. Study of grammatical rules;
3. Using the native language as the main tool in the teaching process;
4. Extensive use of translation exercises;
5. Greater emphasis on reading and writing skills¹

The advantage of the above methods is to understand the language system based on strict rules and develop written speech skills. Also, from the 1840s to the 1940s, the grammar-translation method was the dominant method in European and foreign language teaching, and its modified forms are still widely used in some parts of the world today. This method is based on the experience of teaching classical languages such as Latin. In it, the teacher was the central figure, and the main goal of education was to master grammatical rules and vocabulary. This method was mainly aimed at developing reading and writing skills, since the communicative aspect was not

¹ Walia D. N. Traditional teaching methods vs. CLT: A study //Frontiers of language and teaching. – 2012. – T. 3. – №. 1. – C. 125-131.

considered important². The grammar-translation method made a significant contribution to the formation of a systematic approach to teaching foreign languages in its time. It is especially important in that it creates the opportunity for the consistent mastery of grammatical knowledge and in-depth analysis of texts. The fact that this method is still used in some regions today indicates that it has a certain pedagogical effectiveness. In this sense, while recognizing the historical and practical significance of the method, its integration with modern approaches can further improve the language teaching process.

Modern methods prioritize an interactive approach to language teaching, the development of communicative competence, and the use of digital technologies. Unlike traditional methods, they form the student as an active participant³.

Modern pedagogical approaches are aimed at ensuring student activity, effective communication with them, and teaching the language in a real-life context. The main goal of the communicative approach is to use language in practice, to help students master it as a means of communication. This approach involves developing students' skills in expressing, understanding, and listening. The organization of education using immersive technologies and virtual environments allows students to learn the language based on real-life situations. Also, audiovisual tools and multimedia materials make the language teaching process more interesting, dynamic, and effective. Videos, interactive games, audio and video materials interest students in language learning and direct them to the formation of practical skills, which differs from the theoretical approach. Modern methods stimulate students' independent learning activities and ensure the use of language in real communicative situations.

The development of modern language teaching methods serves not only to form communicative competence, but also to develop students' independent thinking, creative approach and problem-solving skills.

The communicative language teaching (CLT) approach focuses on the process of communication rather than on perfect language acquisition. Sometimes the term functional approach is used instead of communicative approach or communicative method. The communicative approach is based on the concept of communicative competence, which was put forward by H. D. Hymes. Hymes introduced this idea into scientific circulation in an article published in the journal *New Origins in Linguistics* in 1971. The main goal of the communicative approach is to emphasize real, meaningful communication, rather than artificial, remote topics and activities from the lives of students⁴. Geeta Nagraj argues that the process of language teaching has evolved from a form-based approach to a content-based approach.

The views put forward by Jack C. Richards, H. Douglas Brown, Stephen Krashen, Diane Larsen-Freeman, and Jeremy Harmer on this issue suggest that traditional methods strengthen the theoretical foundation, while modern methods develop communicative competence. Their integration is the most optimal model of language teaching.

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⁴ Abduraximova, F. K. "Modern approaches and methods in teaching English language." *Экономика и социум* 1-1 (92) (2022): 10-13.